

Using "Memory Strategies" to Enhance EFL Grammar to 6th Secondary Students

Wafaa Mokhlos Faisal, Arshed Sadoun Atei

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: June 28, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: January 29, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Rehearsal, Memory, Imagery, Cognitive, Elaboration</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6335287</p>	<p><i>The current study deals with the effect of utilizing "memory strategies" to enforce learning grammar for 6th secondary students. Various "memory strategies" are regarded as devices to confirm memory since information seems often simple to forget and remember. Thus, the research is primarily related to certain retention procedures which are extremely beneficial to students in memorizing unique grammatical things that have been acquired for the first time. The data was limited to 20 female and male EFL learners in 6th grade who were randomly assigned to a control group and an experimental group after receiving an hour of teaching via Google Classroom. The latter group was given explicit instructions on how utilizing "memory strategies" when learn grammar. The purpose of the post-tests was collecting the relevant information utilizing multiple selection questionnaires. The findings demonstrated which the experimental association's retention of learned structural components improved statistically. Additionally, a crucial statistical difference existed between such two associations.</i></p>

Introduction

1.1 The Research Problem

1. Do memory strategies have an impact on EFL grammar learning?
2. What memory strategies are employed to enforce grammar in 6th grade students?
3. What memory mechanisms are used and how are they used?
4. What effect do they have on EFL grammar learning?

1.2 The problem of the Study

The aim of the current research is to look into impact of utilizing memory techniques to enforce "EFL grammar".

1.3 The Hypotheses

1. "Memory strategies" can be used to reinforce the study of "EFL grammar" and will aid in the recall and retrieval of structural items.
2. Individuals in both the control and experimental groups will have a mean difference in their scores.

1.4 Theoretical Background

In general, "memory techniques" might be thought of as a distinct kind of mental function. In spite of various researchers describe "strategies" in different ways, such strategies always defined as "goal-directed", cognitively taxing processes which are used to impose retention performance. "Strategies" are considered controlled that are achieved consciously via persons. They are most likely accessible to awareness. Other cognitive processes are primarily concerned with strategies, which are influenced by a variety of factors (Courage & Nelson, 2009: 2).

In this context, Oxford (1990) devised a method of language learning technique classification that includes two categories: indirect and direct strategies. Direct strategies are those that employ language in a way which directly includes the concerned language. "All direct tactics" necessitate language processing in the brain.

Figure (1)

"Classification of learning strategies, Oxford: 1990"

These are divided into three categories: memory, cognition and compensatory, and the focus of this research is on "memory methods" and how to use them to improve EFL grammar teaching.

It is worth noting that "memory tactics" is also known as mnemonics. That is, they are clearly more successful when the learner employs meta-cognitive tactics such as affective strategies and paying attention, such as deep breathing to reduce fear. They also frequently involve mixing and matching different types of materials. It is possible to supply verbal labels to make visual images of words or phrases, to pictures, or to connect the verbal within the visual in terms of "language learning" for four causes:

1. The ability of mind store visible information outperforms its ability to store verbal information.
2. Visible pictures are used to send the most effectively packaged bits of information to long-term retention.
3. Visible pictures can be the most effective tool for remembering verbal information.
4. Visual learning is more effective when a large group of pupils is involved.

Indirect strategies are the second type of learner strategy identified by Oxford (1990: 137). Meta-cognitive, social, and affective strategies are three types of such tactics. Meta-cognitive tactics such as "arranging," "centering," "planning," and "evaluating" help pupils "coordinate" and "cognition" their learning. They are divided into three strategic groups: planning, learning, and planning your learning, as well as evaluating your learning.

Furthermore, Oxford (1990: 71) defined "affective strategies" as procedures that allow pupils to influence their emotions, motivations, and perspectives when learning a language. She (ibid) defined three core sets of affective strategies: self-encouragement, anxiety reduction, and emotional temperature monitoring. Deep breathing, progressive relaxation, or meditation, as well as music and laughter, can all help to reduce anxiety. When it comes to motivating yourself, you can listen to your body, write a language learning diary, use a checklist, and talk about your emotions with someone else (ibid: 141).

Social strategies, for Oxford (1990), are skills which enable students to "facilitate engagement with others, often in a discourse environment" (p. 71). It is categorized social techniques into three categories: working with others, asking questions, and focusing on one another. Questioning for verification, clarification, or correction is one type of questioning. Cooperation with proficient users and peers of the novel language is, nonetheless, one of the cooperative tactics, (ibid).

As a result, Oxford (1990) divided "memory strategies" into four categories, each with its own set of techniques.

a. Creating Cognitive Connections

It employs methods such as association, grouping, and contextualization to place new words in context.

b. Using Sound and Imagery

It employs lexical mapping, imagery, keyword usage, and sound memory mapping methodologies.

c. Thoroughly reviewing.

It can be accomplished via structured feeding back mechanisms.

d. Putting Acting to Work.

It is treated with by the use of bodily sense or response, as well as mechanical technology. Retention strategies like as cognitive imagery, elaboration, mnemonics, rehearsal, and organizing that are effective in retrieving knowledge, must be used to improve grammar learning, (Santrock, 2011: 63).

- **Elaboration** is the process of adding distinctiveness to new knowledge, and it demonstrates elaboration tactics. Elaboration, according to Woolfolk (2013: 78), aids in the retrieval and encoding of fresh information since it connects new and old knowledge.
- **Mental imagery** refers to the process of envisioning images of linguistic data in order to construct cognitive imagery. In this context, Paivio (1971: 76) noted that when relevant visual information is triggered, linguistic memory may improve. The information is binary coded as a result of this activation.
- **Mnemonics** are words and images that can be put together as mnemonics to aid memory. The following are examples of "mnemonic strategies": "rhymes", such as "righty tighty, lefty loosey," song lyrics, such as "head and shoulders, knees and toes," phrases, such as "never eat soggy waffles" to remember the compass directions "north, east, south, and west," The states of Michigan, Ontario, Superior, and Erie ", loci method (e.g., "use the logical movement after supper to remember "a tiger" on the counter, "a monkey" in the sink, "a hippo" in the dishwasher, and "a bald eagle" on the sofa"), keyword methods.
- **Organization** refers to connecting of elements together in such a way that recalling one phrase also recalls other terms related to it. Santrock (2011: 89) discussed that structure helps to make a big amount of data more relevant and manageable. Woolfolk (2013: 67) also proposed using hierarchy to emerge pieces of knowledge, chunking to aggregate information to higher-order things being recalled as elementary units, and using outline to organize information.
- **Rehearsal** draws attention to ongoing training information, which can help to lengthen the duration that information is retained in memory. In this regard, Santrock (2011: 78) claimed that keeping a record functions best when remembering and encoding a collection of objects for a short length of time, but not when preserving information for a long period of time. In this regard, Woolfolk (2013: 78) emphasized that "rehearsal" works effectively severely overlearned material, like, multiplication tables, spelling words, or playwriting, but not with more important and sophisticated information. Although the human mind has the capacity to store roughly "100" trillion bits of data, such massive storage cannot be accessed without the use of "memory techniques" (Oxford, 1990: 38). As a result, the current study examined the impact of using "memory methods," particularly "acting" and "applying visuals and sounds" on EFL students' memory.

1.5 Literature Review

The aim of the present section is to revisit topics concerned with language learning strategies generally, as well as "memory strategies" particularly. Despite there are various researches on utilizing "memory methods" to develop vocabulary, English language education needs studies on utilizing "memory strategies" to improve "EFL grammar acquisition". As a result, a few studies have been conducted to see if particular "memory methods" can help with "grammar augmentation."

Heuer (1999: 24) stated that in order to transmit new information from short-term retention to long-term retention, it is necessary to consider a schema that already presents in retention. This is based on double "variables," amount of processing provided to novel data and the extent to which the data is dealt with by the schemata. However, he (ibid) stated that if novel information does not "fit" into a presenting memory schema or structure, mnemonic devices should be used to "commit" information into retention.

Based on "memory strategies" within the classroom, lecturers' memory strategy teachings are missing in the intensity required for learners to learn how to utilize "memory strategies" effectively. Furthermore, instructors use a wide range of memory-relevant vocabulary, such as tactics and meta-cognitive inquiries, to help students to retain information. While learning is important, recall and retention of the units learned should not be overlooked. The ability to remember or recall things after a certain period of time is passed is referred to as language unit retention (Richards & Schmitt, 2002: 457).

Similarly, recognizing the value of "mnemonic devices" by demonstrating that those can help a learner acquire recall and remember faster and better by integrating novel content into presented mental unit and supplying retrieval cues. "Mnemonic devices" have been proven being successful at all times. They are, nevertheless, more effective for low-degree learners since they are usually used in tasks that need them to recall and overlearned information.

Memory methods are considered to be one of the most successful strategies for "learning EFL grammar" and are extremely powerful cognitive resources. According to Oxford (1990: 38), the brain can store about 100 trillion pieces of knowledge, but solely a fraction of that capacity can be utilized until "memory techniques"

come to the learners' aid. Utilizing "memory techniques" generally entails connecting various kinds of information. LLSs, according to Weinstein and Mayer (1986: 60), are "behaviors and thoughts" that students participate in when learning and have an impact on their "encoding process." LLSs are "techniques, approaches, or deliberate activities that students use to facilitate the learning and recall of both language and content area information." For Chamot (2004: 71), LLSs mean "techniques, approaches or deliberate actions that students take in order to facilitate the learning and recall of both linguistic and content area information".

As a result, Schmitt (1997: 216) defined "memory techniques" as "strategies that include relating words to some previously learned awareness through the use of imagery or grouping." As a result, according to Macaro (2001: 118), MSs serve by "processing" vocabulary or word items in "working memory" so that they may be recovered and stored from long-term retention. The manner these tactics obtained the chunk of language could be the same as how it was stocked.

In this study, we'd like to emphasize on the critical function of "memory techniques" in improving the learning process new grammar items and recalling them as soon as feasible. The major themes are the purpose of teachers' roles, memory enhancing techniques and tools, and teaching procedures in which students are grouped together in a single package of instruction.

1.6 Methodology

A. Research plan

The study used an experimental design in which two associations were chosen at random, and a pre-test was used to establish the two groups' starting background knowledge, as well as a post-test to obtain the relevant data.

B. Participants.

Both organisations' concerned members were chosen at random from Baat Al- Gadeer School for boys and girls. This study's sample size is twenty students for the academic year 2021-2022. There are "20" pupils in total, with "10" students in each association.

C. Procedures

This research was conducted based on three phases:

The first phase was a pre-test, in which learners were assessed before implementing "memory methods" into the classroom. The concerned goal is to determine learners' prior awareness. The time limit for the current phase was set at thirty minute. Each association was asked "ten" questions, and each question carries a certain weight (1 M).

Phase two: Individuals from the two groups were given lessons in this phase, whereas the control association was given presentations without utilizing "memory methods" and received no special treatment. The experimental association, on the other hand, was introduced utilizing unique "memory methods" such as using image, acting, mnemonics, and sound. An hour has been set aside for such a face.

Post-test, phase three is slowed. The effect of using "memory methods" when teaching grammar was the independent variable. The pupils' "EFL grammar reservation" was "dependent variables." The subjects were examined a week later to obtain the findings of the current investigation and to see if there was important distinction between these two connections. As a result, both groups were given 25 questions to answer.

Thus, both courses were held utilizing "Power Point Presentation," with the class dealing with learning of the present simple tense, the use of adjectives and auxiliaries to separate things, and explanation of cause and effect clauses.

The experimental association is denoted by Group A. It was taught through the use of "memory methods." As a result, the participants were introduced to the concept of strategy through a presentation that included simple descriptions of the two types of memory as well as examples to demonstrate them. In each type of strategy, items were given in a different way. Group B refers to the control group, which was taught without the use of any effective "memory methods," instead relying exclusively on repetition strategies.

1.7 Data analysis

The study's findings were examined both statistically and descriptively. The SPSS application (Version 20) was utilized to investigate the relevant data gained from the tools (post-test and pre-test). As a result, it was begun to analyze the data of both associations' pre-tests for perceiving the background of both experimental and control associations, and it was discovered that the concerned data were relatively identical and that there was no significant difference between them prior to implementing the treatment.

Table (1). The Outcomes of Pre-Test

"Experimental"	2	2	3	2	3	4	2	3	3	4
"Control"	3	2	2	1	2	3	4	4	2	1

Group Statistics

EXPERIMENTAL	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
CONTROL 1.00	10	2.4000	1.07497	.33993
CONTROL 2.00	10	2.4000	1.07497	.33993

As a result, the post-test results must be analyzed over two associations, a control and an experimental, in order to determine how much the independent variable influences the dependent variable and respond to the research questions.

Table (2) The Findings of Post-Test.

NO	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
"Experimental"	5	6	6	5	7	9	7	7	7	9
"Control"	5	4	4	3	5	5	4	6	4	3

Group Statistics

	VAR00001	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Posttest	1.00	10	6.8000	1.39841	.44222
	2.00	10	4.3000	.94868	.30000

Independent Samples Test

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Posttest	Equal variances assumed	.775	.390	4.678	18	.000	2.50000	.53437	1.37732	3.62268
	Equal variances not assumed			4.678	15.836	.000	2.50000	.53437	1.36622	3.63378

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Posttest	20	3.00	9.00	5.5500	1.73129
VAR00001	20	1.00	2.00	1.5000	.51299
Valid N (listwise)	20				

"Independent sample" test is indicated to assess conceivable distinctions between tools of control and experimental groups depended on the attained outcomes from the post-test after displaying data to SPSS and using t-test. The experimental group's tool receives a score of (5.5), while the control group's tool receives a score of (1.5), and standard deviations is (1.7) for experimental association and (0512) for control association.

Conclusion

The current study's findings assist students in becoming more conscious of how to use "memory tactics" in EFL classrooms. The control and experimental groups had different mean outcomes in the post tests, indicating which adopting "memory methods" can have an effect on "EFL grammar acquisition", according to statistical analysis. As a result, there is a significant distinction between teaching that relies on classical tactics and teaching that relies on "memory strategies" inside learners' "grammar learning" retentions.

Bibliography

- Chamot, A. U. (2004). *Issues in language learning strategy research and teaching*. *Electronic Journal of Foreign Language Teaching*, 1, 14-26. Retrieved March 20, 2011, from <http://e-flt.nus.edu.sg/v1n12004/chamot>.
- Heuer, R. J. (1999). *Psychology of intelligence analysis*. Washington DC: Centre for the Study of Intelligence.
- Levin, J. R. (1994). "memory strategies" and classroom learning: A twenty-year report card. *The Elementary School Journal*, 94, 235-244.
- Macaro, E. (2001). *Learning strategies in second and foreign language classrooms*. London: Continuum.
- Nelson, D.L., & Quick, J.C. (2009). *Organizational Behavior: Science, the Real World and You*, 6th (Ed.). Mason, OH: Southwestern/Cengage
- Oxford, R.L. (1990). *Language learning strategies: What every teacher should know*. Boston: Heinle&Heinle.
- Paivio, A. (1971). *Imagery and verbal processes*. New York: Holt, Rinehart, & Winston.
- Santrock, J. W. (2011). *Educational Psychology*. (5th ed.). New York: McGraw-Hill
- Schmitt, N. (1997). Vocabulary learning strategies. In N. Schmitt & M. McCarthy (Eds.), *Vocabulary: description, acquisition and pedagogy* (pp.199-228). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Weinstein, C., & Mayer, R. (1986). *The teaching of learning strategies*. New York: Macmillan.
- Woolfolk, A. E. (2013). *Educational Psychology*. Boston: Pearson.

Author Information

Asst. Prof. Dr. Wafaa Mokhlos Faisal

University of Babylon/ college of Education for Human Sciences/ English Dep.
Educational Directorate Babylon, Ministry of Education, Iraq

Arshed Sadoun Atei

University of Babylon/ college of Education for Human Sciences/ English Dep.
Educational Directorate Babylon, Ministry of Education, Iraq
